

THE ROLE OF INTERACTION IN E-LEARNING

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ABSTRACT: This article studies the role of interaction in distance education and for teaching and learning the English language. It is vital to mention that the work is devoted to highlight the effects of e-learning..

KEY WORDS: Distance education, Types of Interaction, Web-Based Instruction (WBI), online questioning, answering, discussion, debate, negotiation, face-to-face communication.

Distance education provides a mechanism that has become widely used in academia; therefore, it is necessary that instructional designers and curriculum developers are able to design effective instruction that meets the needs of students in a distance education environment.

Educators and course paperers alike have questioned the idea that online courses provide sufficient and adequate interaction. This debate has been the topic of numerous course paper studies and continues to be investigated using various instructional strategies. Critics believe that interaction is the missing ingredient in the e-learning equation, while proponents strongly believe that interaction in online courses is equal to or greater than interaction in traditional classrooms.

The literature reveals that the traditional concepts of interaction have provided a rich area for course paper within the field of e-learning.

Defining Interaction

Distance educators have struggled with how to describe the concept of interaction clearly. Interactions occur when these objects and events mutually influence one another. An instructional interaction is an event that takes place between a learner and the learner's environment. Its purpose is to respond to the learner in a way intended to change his or her behavior toward and educational goal.

Weller believes that interaction serves as a gateway for learners to adjust the instruction to meet their needs and capabilities so that they can receive feedback as a consequence of their actions. Merrill, Li, and Jones discuss instructional as interaction between the learner and technology that is mutual, dynamic, and real time. Students tend to define interaction as communication and feedback between and among instructors and students rather than activities completed or technologies used in the classroom.

Types of Interaction. The type of interaction that takes place between the learner and the content is the most fundamental of the four types. The process that has traditionally been identified as “learning” takes place when a student interacts with the subject matter or course content. This content can be in the form of a paper-based text, radio or television programming, audio or videotape, or, it can be in a computer-implemented form such as a CD, computer program, digital audio/video, or Web-based. Northrup adds that interacting with content is where new knowledge, skills, and abilities are presented¹.

A second type of interaction occurs between the learner and the instructor. Many regard this form of interaction as essential for teaching and learning. The instructor serves as an expert who develops instruction to stimulate student’s interests and to motivate their participation in the learning process. Learner-instructor interaction can vary from the instructor providing lecture through didactic, coaching, and Socratic formats to the instructor interacting one-on-one with a student.

Historically, there have been limited opportunities for integrating the third type of interaction, learner-learner interaction, into educational settings. Instead, concerns have focused on the areas of learner- content and learner-instructor interaction. The development of distance education technology has made it increasingly possible for learners to interact with one another. The interaction between learners can take place in real or delayed time without the presence of the instructor asserts that learner-learner interaction can be an extremely valuable and essential resource for learning; yet, pros and cons have emerged from this type of interaction. Course paper indicates that providing students with opportunities to interact with each other increases student motivation, learning satisfaction, and fosters learning through collaboration and knowledge sharing².

Hillman argues that the fourth type of interaction evolved as a result of distance education technologies and blended learning Hillman et al describes learner-interface interaction as the interaction that takes place between the learner and the technology used to implement the distance education process. The students are forced to use the technology to interact with at least the content and the instructor.

Aside from the traditional types of interaction, the fundamental characteristics of a Web system allows its users to interact with content by reading text, searching instruction, and linking content. This type of interaction gives users dynamic control of information, allowing individuals to explore abundant and diverse bits of information in their own ways. To this extent, Lacy and Wood argue that content interaction in Web-Based Instruction (WBI) is able to approach constructivist pedagogy.

Educators issues with WBI also focus on social interaction and whether the online format provides adequate opportunities for this type of interaction. Liaw and Huang point out that social interaction usually involves face-to-face communication; however, when discussing social interaction in a Web system, face-to-face communication is not necessary; for instance, “when learners need to ask or instructors need to answer questions, WBI provides e-mail, newsgroups, discussion boards or computer conferences” (p. 43). In support of social interaction in an online environment, Yang contends that a WBI system provides enormous potential for social interaction. Yang argues that in this system, learners and instructors or learners and learners can engage in online questioning, answering, discussion, debate, or negotiation without face-to-face communication.

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